

A New Trend of Neutrosophic Closed Sets in Neutrosophic Topological Spaces

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Abstract:

In this paper, we have introduced a new types of Neutrosophic Vartheta closed sets in neutrosophic topological spaces which are a stronger form. Particularly we proved that the result of finite union of any two N_{θ} CSs in (X, τ_N) is also N_{θ} CS in (X, τ_N) . Moreover, we investigate some of their basic properties and justify them with counter examples in Neutrosophic topological spaces.

Keywords: N_{θ} CS, N_{θ} OS, N_{θ} int(A), N_{θ} cl(A), Neutrosophic sets.

AMS Mathematics Subject Classification: 18B30, 03E72

Introduction:

Neutrosophic set initially proposed by Florentin Samarandache[1] which is a generalization of Atanassov's intuitionistic fuzzy sets and Zadeh's fuzzy sets. Also it considers truth-membership function, indeterminacy-membership function and falsity-membership function. Since fuzzy sets and intuitionistic fuzzy sets fails to deal with indeterminacy-membership functions, Smarandache introduced the neutrosophic concept in various fields, including probability, algebra, control theory, topology, etc. Later Alblowi et al., [5] introduced neutrosophic set based concepts in the neutrosophic field. These effective concepts has been applied by many researchers in the last two decades to propose many concepts in topology. Salama and Alblowi [5] proposed a new concept in neutrosophic topological spaces and it provides a brief idea about

neutrosophic topology, which is a generalization of Coker's intuitionistic fuzzy topology and Chang's fuzzy topology. In 2016, P. Iswarya, Dr. K. Bageerathi[3] introduced the concept of neutrosophic semi open and closed sets. In 2018, R.Dhavaseelan and S.Jafari[2] introduced the new class of Neutrosophic closed sets namely as Generalized neutrosophic closed sets. Aim of this paper is we introduce and study about Neutrosophic Vartheta closed sets (N_{θ} CS) in neutrosophic closed sets and its properties and characterization are discussed with details.

Ground Work:

In this section, we recall needed basic definition and operation of Neutrosophic sets and its fundamental Results which was already defined by various authors.

B₁ Definition: Let X be a non empty fixed set. A neutrosophic set B is an object having the form $B = \{ \langle x, Tv(B(x)), Iv(B(x)), Fv(B(x)) \rangle \forall x \in X \}$, where $Tv(B(x))$ represents the degree of membership, $Iv(B(x))$ represents the degree of indeterminacy and $Fv(B(x))$ represents the degree of non-membership functions of each element $x \in X$ to the set B .

B₂ Note: A neutrosophic set $B = \{ \langle x, Tv(B(x)), Iv(B(x)), Fv(B(x)) \rangle \forall x \in X \}$ can be identified to an ordered triple $\langle x, Tv(B(x)), Iv(B(x)), Fv(B(x)) \rangle$ in $]0, 1^+[$ on X .

B₃ Defintion: Let B and C be two neutrosophic sets of the form, $B = \{ \langle x, Tv(B(x)), Iv(B(x)), Fv(B(x)) \rangle \forall x \in X \}$ and $C = \{ \langle x, Tv(C(x)), Iv(C(x)), Fv(C(x)) \rangle \forall x \in X \}$. Then,

- i. $B \subseteq C$ iff $Tv(B(x)) \subseteq Tv(C(x)), Iv(B(x)) \subseteq Iv(C(x)), Fv(B(x)) \supseteq Fv(C(x)) \forall x \in X$,
- ii. $B = C$ iff $B \subseteq C$ and $B \supseteq C$,
- iii. $\bar{B} = \{ \langle x, Tv(C(x)), 1 - Iv(C(x)), Fv(C(x)) \rangle \forall x \in X \}$
- iv. $B \cup C = \{ \langle x, \max[Tv(B(x)), Tv(C(x))], \max[Iv(B(x)), Iv(C(x))], \min[Fv(B(x)), Fv(C(x))] \rangle \forall x \in X \}$,
- v. $B \cap C = \{ \langle x, \min[Tv(B(x)), Tv(C(x))], \min[Iv(B(x)), Iv(C(x))], \max[Fv(B(x)), Fv(C(x))] \rangle \forall x \in X \}$

B₄ Definition A neutrosophic topology on a non-empty set X is a family τ_N of neutrosophic subsets in satisfying the following axioms:

- i. $0_N, 1_N \in \tau_N$
- ii. $B_1 \cap B_2 \in \tau_N$ for any $B_1, B_2 \in \tau_N$
- iii. $\cup B_i \in \tau_N \forall \{B_i: i \in J\} \subseteq \tau_N$

Then the pair (X, τ_N) or X is called a neutrosophic topological space.

B₅ Definition A neutrosophic set B in a neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) is called

- i. A neutrosophic semiclosed[3] set(briefly N_sCS) if $Nint(Ncl(B)) \subseteq B$
- ii. A neutrosophic preclosed[7] set(briefly N_pCS) if $Ncl(Nint(B)) \subseteq B$
- iii. A neutrosophic α -closed[4] set(briefly $N_{\alpha}CS$) if $Ncl(Nint(Ncl(B))) \subseteq B$
- iv. A neutrosophic regular closed[6] set(briefly N_rCS) if $Ncl(Nint(B)) = B$

B₆ Definition A neutrosophic set B in a neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) is called

- i. A neutrosophic generalized closed set (briefly N_gCS) if $Ncl(B) \subseteq V$ whenever $B \subseteq V$ and V is N_oS .
- ii. A neutrosophic generalized pre closed set (briefly $N_{gp}CS$) if $Npcl(B) \subseteq V$ whenever $B \subseteq V$ and V is N_oS .
- iii. A neutrosophic generalized semi closed set (briefly $N_{gs}CS$) if $Nscl(B) \subseteq V$ whenever $B \subseteq V$ and V is N_oS .
 A neutrosophic α -generalized closed set (briefly $N_{\alpha g}CS$) if $N\alpha cl(B) \subseteq V$ whenever $B \subseteq V$ and V is N_oS .
- iv. A neutrosophic semi generalized closed set (briefly $N_{sg}CS$) if $Nscl(B) \subseteq V$ whenever $B \subseteq V$ and V is $N_{so}S$.

Neutrosophic Vartheta Closed Sets

C₁ Definition:

Let B be a subset of a Neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) is said to be Neutrosophic- ϑ -closed ($N_{\vartheta}CS$) if $Ncl(Nint(B)) \subseteq V$ whenever $B \subseteq V$ and V is a Neutrosophic Generalized open set in (X, τ_N) .

The family of all Neutrosophic- ϑ -closed sets of a neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) is denoted by $C_{N_{\vartheta}}(X)$

C₂ Illustration: Let $X = \{B_1, B_2, B_3\}$, $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, P, Q\}$ be a neutrosophic topology on X . Where

$$P = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right), \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right), \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right) \right\}$$

$$Q = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{7}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10} \right), \left(\frac{7}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{6}{10} \right), \left(\frac{7}{10}, \frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10} \right) \right\}$$

Then the Neutrosophic set $R = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{8}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right), \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{8}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right), \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{9}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right) \right\}$ is a $N_{\vartheta}CS$ in X . But the Neutrosophic set

$$S = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right), \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right), \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right) \right\}$$
 is not a $N_{\vartheta}CS$ in X .

C₃ Proposition: In the neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) , if a subset B is a Neutrosophic closed set then it is a $N_{\vartheta}CS$. But not conversely.

Proof: Let $B \subseteq V$ and V is a Neutrosophic g -open set in (X, τ_N) . Since B is a Neutrosophic closed set, $Ncl(Nint(B)) \subseteq Ncl(B) = B \subseteq V$. Therefore B is Neutrosophic ϑ -closed set in X .

C₄ Illustration : Let $X = \{B_1, B_2\}$, $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, P, Q\}$ be a neutrosophic topology on X . Where

$$P = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{1}{10}, \frac{4}{10} \right), \left(\frac{7}{10}, \frac{1}{10}, \frac{2}{10} \right) \right\}$$

$$Q = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{1}{10}, \frac{1}{10}, \frac{8}{10} \right), \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{1}{10}, \frac{8}{10} \right) \right\}$$

Then the Neutrosophic set $R = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{1}{10}, \frac{6}{10} \right), \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{1}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right) \right\}$ is a $N_{\vartheta}CS$, but not a Neutrosophic closed set in X , since $Ncl(R) = P^c \neq R$.

C₅ Proposition: In the neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) , if a subset B is a Neutrosophic semi closed set then it is a $N_{\vartheta}CS$. But not conversely.

Proof: Let $B \subseteq V$ and V is a Neutrosophic g -open set in (X, τ_N) . Since B is a Neutrosophic semi closed set, $Ncl(Nint(B)) \subseteq Nscl(B) = B \subseteq V$. Therefore B is Neutrosophic- ϑ -closed in X .

C₆ Illustration: Let $X = \{B_1, B_2\}$, $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, P\}$ be a neutrosophic topology on X . Where

$$P = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10} \right), \left(\frac{8}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10} \right) \right\}$$

Then the Neutrosophic set $Q = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10} \right), \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10} \right) \right\}$ is a $N_{\vartheta}CS$, but not a Neutrosophic semi closed set in X , since $Nint(Ncl(Q)) = 1_N \not\subseteq Q$.

C₇ Proposition: In the neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) , if a subset B is a Neutrosophic pre closed set then it is a $N_{\vartheta}CS$. But not conversely.

Proof: Let $B \subseteq V$ and V is a Neutrosophic g -open set in (X, τ_N) . Since B is a Neutrosophic pre closed set, $(Nint(B)) \subseteq B \subseteq V$. Therefore B is $N_{\vartheta}CS$ in X .

C₈ Illustration : Let $X = \{B_1\}$, $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, P, Q\}$ be a neutrosophic topology on X . Where $P = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10} \right) \right\}$

$Q = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{1}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10} \right) \right\}$. Then the Neutrosophic set $R = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{3}{10}, \frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10} \right) \right\}$ is a $N_{\vartheta}CS$ but not a Neutrosophic pre closed set in X , since $Ncl(Nint(R)) = P^c \not\subseteq R$.

C₉ Proposition: In the neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) , if a subset B is a Neutrosophic regular closed set then it is a $N_{\vartheta}CS$. But not conversely.

Proof: Let $B \subseteq V$ and V is a Neutrosophic g -open set in (X, τ_N) . Since B is a Neutrosophic regular closed set, $(Nint(B)) = B$. This implies $Ncl(B) = Ncl(Nint(B))$, $Ncl(B) = B$. Hence B is a Neutrosophic closed set in X . By proposition (C₁), B is $N_{\vartheta}CS$ in X .

C₁₀ Illustration : Let $X = \{B_1, B_2\}$, $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, P, Q\}$ be a neutrosophic topology on X . Where

$$P = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right), \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right), \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right) \right\}$$

$$Q = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{7}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10} \right), \left(\frac{7}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{6}{10} \right), \left(\frac{7}{10}, \frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10} \right) \right\}$$

Then the Neutrosophic set $R = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{8}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right), \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{8}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right), \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{9}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right) \right\}$ is a N_gCS but not a Neutrosophic regular closed set in X , since $Ncl(Nint(R)) = P^c \neq R$.

C₁₁ Proposition: In the neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) , if a subset B is a Neutrosophic- α -closed set then it is a N_gCS . But not conversely.

Proof: Let $B \subseteq V$ and V is a Neutrosophic g -open set in (X, τ_N) . Since B is a Neutrosophic alpha closed set, $Nacl(B) = B$. This implies $Ncl(Nint(B)) \subseteq Nacl(B) = B \subseteq V$.

Hence B is a N_gCS in X .

C₁₂ Illustration : Let $X = \{B_1, B_2\}$, $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, P\}$ be a neutrosophic topology on X . Where

$$P = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10} \right), \left(\frac{8}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10} \right) \right\}$$

Then the Neutrosophic set $Q = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10} \right), \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10} \right) \right\}$ is a N_gCS but not a Neutrosophic alpha closed set in X , since $Ncl(Nint(Ncl(Q))) = 1_N \not\subseteq Q$.

C₁₃ Proposition: In the neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) , if a subset B is a Neutrosophic- g - closed set then it is a N_gCS . But not conversely.

Proof: Let $B \subseteq V$ and B is a Neutrosophic g -open set in (X, τ_N) . Since B is a Neutrosophic generalized closed set, $Ncl(B) \subseteq V$. Therefore $Ncl(Nint(B)) \subseteq Ncl(B)$, $Ncl(Nint(B)) \subseteq V$. Hence B is a N_gCS in X .

C₁₄ Illustration : Let $X = \{B_1, B_2\}$, $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, P\}$ be a neutrosophic topology on X . Where

$$P = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10} \right), \left(\frac{8}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10} \right) \right\}$$

Then the Neutrosophic set $Q = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10} \right), \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10} \right) \right\}$ is a N_gCS but not a Neutrosophic generalized closed set in X , since $Ncl(Q) = 1_N \not\subseteq Q$.

C₁₅ Proposition: In the neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) , if a subset B is a Neutrosophic- gp - closed set then it is a N_gCS . But not conversely.

Proof: Let $B \subseteq V$ and B is a Neutrosophic g -open set in (X, τ_N) . Since B is a Neutrosophic generalized pre closed set, $Npcl(B) \subseteq V$. Therefore $Ncl(Nint(B)) \subseteq Npcl(B)$, $Ncl(Nint(B)) \subseteq V$. Hence B is a N_gCS in X .

C₁₆ Illustration: Let $X = \{B_1, B_2, B_3\}$, $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, P, Q, R, S\}$ be a neutrosophic topology on X . Where

$$P = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{3}{10}, \frac{4}{10}, \frac{2}{10} \right), \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right), \left(\frac{9}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10} \right) \right\}$$

$$Q = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{1}{10} \right), \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{2}{10} \right), \left(\frac{8}{10}, \frac{4}{10}, \frac{6}{10} \right) \right\}, R = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{1}{10} \right), \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}, \frac{2}{10} \right), \left(\frac{9}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10} \right) \right\}$$

$$S = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{3}{10}, \frac{4}{10}, \frac{2}{10} \right), \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right), \left(\frac{8}{10}, \frac{4}{10}, \frac{6}{10} \right) \right\}, T = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}, \frac{1}{10} \right), \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{7}{10}, \frac{1}{10} \right), \left(\frac{9}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10} \right) \right\}$$

Then the Neutrosophic set $U = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{4}{10} \right), \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10} \right), \left(\frac{3}{10}, \frac{4}{10}, \frac{8}{10} \right) \right\}$ is a N_gCS in X . But not a Ngp -closed, since $Npcl(U) = U \not\subseteq R$.

C₁₇ Proposition: In the neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) , if a subset B is a Neutrosophic- αg - closed set then it is a N_gCS . But not conversely.

Proof: Let $B \subseteq V$ and V is a Neutrosophic g -open set in (X, τ_N) . Since B is a Neutrosophic α -generalized closed set, $Nacl(B) \subseteq V$. Therefore $Ncl(Nint(B)) \subseteq Nacl(B)$, $Ncl(Nint(B)) \subseteq V$. Hence B is a N_gCS in X .

C₁₈ Illustration: Let $X = \{B_1, B_2\}$, $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, P\}$ be a neutrosophic topology on X . Where

$$P = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10} \right), \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10} \right) \right\}$$

Then the Neutrosophic set $R = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10} \right), \left(\frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right) \right\}$ is a N_gCS but not a Neutrosophic αg -closed set in X , since $acl(R) = 1_N \not\subseteq P$.

C₁₉ Proposition: In the neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) , if a subset B is a N_gCS then it is a NSG-closed set. But conversely not true.

Proof: Let $B \subseteq V$, where V is neutrosophic semi-open in X . Since B is N_gCS , $Ncl(Nint(B)) = B$. But $NScl \subseteq Ncl(Nint(B)) = B$, which implies $NScl(B) \subseteq V$. Therefore B is neutrosophic SG-closed set.

C₂₀ Illustration: Let $X = \{B_1, B_2, B_3\}$, $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, P, Q\}$ be a neutrosophic topology on X . Where

$$P = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right), \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right), \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right) \right\}$$

$$Q = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{7}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10} \right), \left(\frac{7}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{6}{10} \right), \left(\frac{7}{10}, \frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10} \right) \right\}$$

Then the Neutrosophic set $R = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right), \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right), \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right) \right\}$ is NSG-closed set but not a N_gCS in X , since $Ncl(Nint(R)) = Q^c \not\subseteq R^c$.

C₂₁ Proposition: In the Neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) , if a subset B is a N_gCS – closed set then it is a NGS-closed set. But conversely not true.

Proof: Let $\subseteq V$, where V is Neutrosophic open in X . Since B is $N_\theta CS$, $Ncl(Nint(B)) = B$. But $NScl(B) \subseteq Ncl(Nint(B)) = B$, which implies $NScl(B) \subseteq V$. Therefore B is Neutrosophic GS -closed set.

C₂₂ Illustration: Let $X = \{B_1, B_2, B_3\}$, $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, P, Q\}$ be a neutrosophic topology on X . Where

$$P = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right), \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right), \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right) \right\}$$

$$Q = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{7}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10} \right), \left(\frac{7}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{6}{10} \right), \left(\frac{7}{10}, \frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10} \right) \right\}$$

Then the Neutrosophic set $R = \left\{ X, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right), \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right), \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{7}{10} \right) \right\}$ is NGS -closed set but not a $N_\theta CS$ in X , since $Ncl(Nint(R)) = Q^c \not\subseteq R^c$.

C₂₃ Proposition: The union of any two $N_\theta CS$ s in (X, τ_N) is also $N_\theta CS$ in (X, τ_N) .

Proof: Let B and C be two $N_\theta CS$ s in (X, τ_N) . Let V be a Neutrosophic generalized open set in X such that $B \subseteq V$ and $C \subseteq V$. Then we have, $B \cup C \subseteq V$. Since B and C are $N_\theta CS$ s in (X, τ_N) , which implies $Ncl(Nint(B)) \subseteq V$ and $Ncl(Nint(C)) \subseteq V$. Now, $Ncl(Nint(B \cup C)) = Ncl(Nint(B)) \cup Ncl(Nint(C)) \subseteq V$. Thus, we have $Ncl(Nint(B \cup C)) \subseteq V$ whenever $B \cup C \subseteq V$, V is Neutrosophic g -open set in (X, τ_N) which implies $B \cup C$ is $N_\theta CS$ in (X, τ_N) .

C₂₄ Proposition: Let B be a N_θ -closed subset in (X, τ_N) . If $B \subseteq C \subseteq Ncl(Nint(B))$, then C is also a N_θ -closed subset in (X, τ_N) .

Proof: Let $C \subseteq V$, where V is neutrosophic generalized open set in (X, τ_N) . Then $B \subseteq C$ implies $B \subseteq V$. Since B is N_θ -closed, $Ncl(Nint(B)) \subseteq V$. Also $C \subseteq Ncl(Nint(B))$ implies $Ncl(Nint(C)) \subseteq Ncl(Nint(B))$. Thus $Ncl(Nint(C)) \subseteq V$ and so C is $N_\theta CS$.

The following implications are true:

Conclusion:

In this study, we present the notions of N_θ -closed sets in neutrosophic topological space and studied different types of closed we formulate some results on neutrosophic topological spaces in the form of Theorems, Propositions, etc. We provide few illustrative counter examples where the results fail. We hope that, in the future, based on these notions and various closed and open sets on the same area, many new investigation / research can be done.

Acknowledgments: The authors would like to thank the referees for useful comments and suggestions.

Conflicts of interest: The author declares that there are no conflicts of interest.

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